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Author Correction: The endocannabinoid hydrolase FAAH is an allosteric enzyme

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Correction to: *Scientific Reports* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-59120-1>, published online 10 February 2020

In the original version of this Article, Alice Ballone was incorrectly affiliated with ‘Faculty of Biosciences, and Technology for Food Agriculture and Environment, University of Teramo, Teramo, Italy’. The correct affiliation is listed below.

Barcelona Biomedical Research Park (PRBB), University of Pompeu Fabra and Icrea, Barcelona, Spain.

This error has now been corrected in the PDF and HTML versions of the Article.

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